

Analysis of the Legal Treatment of Perfidy

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Abstract. Labor perfidy in Ecuador is a real current problem. There are irregularities in the labor sector that can affect the labor rights of workers, which perpetuates deception and ignorance on the part of those affected. Knowing the causes and consequences of labor perfidy allows projecting solutions to reduce its effect on the working society. The analysis of preliminary studies and surveys defines certain levels of indeterminacy in the answers obtained by a group of lawyers and workers. This integration between neutrosophic sets allows us to reflect, through the representation of neutrosophic statistics, the level of deterioration of the factors that intervene in the violation of labor rights. Consequently, the existing indeterminacy forces carry out the modeling of each element of the group studied to analyze the levels of associated deterioration in Ecuador. As a result, it is defined to propose strategies focused on restructuring regulations to mitigate their impact on the working society of Ecuador.

Keywords: labor perfidy, hiring, deception, rights.

1 Introduction

Perfidy is established as a concept that has been used to denominate a breach of trust or deception, infidelity, or a fault that consists of the infringement or violation of an alleged commitment assumed by two previously established parties [1]. In a general way, it is defined as a form of deception in which the act of a person in good faith is directly compromised. It produces an obvious violation of the rights of the people affected by this action, with adverse effects as it is the deception produced intentionally by the employer towards the worker. This implies a violation of constitutional rights, which may result in the establishment of fines or sanctions for the employer and the worker, and adverse effects on his life, employment, and economic stability.

1.1 Analysis of the Concepts

Below are the basic concepts related to the topic in question:

- **Guarantees:** It can be defined as a legal mechanism to ensure or protect the commitment of a certain obligation that must be fulfilled on time [2]. These guarantees may consist of obtaining the advantage of being liable for the obligation. A guarantee is a mechanism through which it is intended to provide greater protection or security for the fulfillment of the fundamental constitutional rights of all human beings. It is implied that they can be fulfilled effectively.
- **Contract:** A legal relationship whose purpose is the paid provision of services of an economic nature, whether industrial, commercial, or agricultural. More technically, it can be defined as follows: the one whose purpose is the continued provision of private services and economic nature, and for which one of the parties gives a remuneration or reward in exchange for enjoying or using [3], under its dependence or direction, of the professional activity of the other party [4]. The employment contract can be defined as a solemn and bilateral act carried out between two parties called employer and worker. It will establish the necessary conditions to enter into an employment relationship, which also typifies the will of both parties to acquire and provide a job, in exchange for fair remuneration proportional to their activity [5].
- **Obligation:** An obligation can be defined as an act that grants responsibility to fulfill an action immediately and for which one has the right to fulfill, by avoiding its transgression, and being able to be responsible for an act of a debtor towards a creditor. Any legal relationship can be

understood as an obligation by which one of the parties undertakes to make a certain provision to the other which, in correspondence, holds a personal or credit right over the debtor to demand compliance. In addition to responding to the obligated subject with his assets in case of non-compliance.

- **Violation of rights:** The violation consists of an action or omission established in the legal norm, as a condition of the sanction. It should be stated that it is also a breach of a rule, principle, guarantee, or constitutional right. The violation of rights can be defined as those acts in which rights or guarantees established in constitutional rights are violated. These produce harmful effects on the people who are the object of this act, for which it may be subject to sanctions or fines.
- **Job insecurity:** Job insecurity is based on the conditions that a workplace must have to function without causing accidents. These can harm workers, considering that each company or employer must have a contingency plan and security measures in case of misfortune or natural disaster. Therefore, the term occupational safety is understood as those sets of techniques and procedures whose purpose is to avoid, eliminate or minimize the risks that may cause the materialization of accidents at work. This means avoiding injuries and serious effects caused by agents or products of a dangerous nature [6].
- **Work accident:** according to Ecuadorian legislation, it is considered any physical injury caused by misfortune or accident within the workplace. It can be produced by the worker himself due to his lack of experience or training in the development of a function or by a third person when performing a job in a bad way, or by handling machinery incorrectly, which can produce injuries and deterioration of the physical condition, and the shortening of the period of life that depends on the condition of the accident.

1.2 Characteristics of labor perfidy

In general, perfidy, when considered as a concept that is used to name a deception or how it violates an alleged commitment, can be distinguished from other actions by considering the following characteristics:

- **The dishonorable and reprehensible attitude:** In most cases can constitute a crime or betrayal of a person's trust because it can be considered an intentional act and, according to the laws, this act is sanctioned by fines or penalties and custodial sentences. The ignoble attitude is about the actions carried out to cause damage by omission and reproduces the worker or the person involved to commit an error that is foreseen and from which the employer will benefit. A reason why this action can also constitute a crime.
- **Violation of rights (International Humanitarian Law prohibits perfidy as a method to be used in international war conflicts):** This characteristic is not entirely linked to labor law, since it speaks of human rights, in the case of war conflicts in times of war, in which, according to the doctrine, it is an act in which one deceives another with the concept of peace and action contrary to which one lives together is carried out to maintain peace.
- **The abuse of trust:** this characteristic is configured when the employer does not respect the rights of the worker, imposing himself or taking advantage of the respect or determination given by the worker at the time of establishing his employment relationship, for which this falls into labor perfidy. The breach of trust is determined as a criminal type that is contemplated in fraud. This means that those patrimonial injuries that are produced by fraud, are also considered an infraction in which the abuse of trust is denoted. An existing lawful legal relationship between the perpetrator and the corresponding victim; in which the subject considered passive gives his will of free signature, and then the active subject abuses the expressed good faith that has been delivered to him, violates any action raised in an unjustified manner.

The abuse of trust by the worker in the case of perfidy is directly related to the abuse of the will of the worker, who trusts his employer. The disappointment of any situation in which the worker himself may be affected is facilitated.

In general, the characteristics that constitute perfidy are basic concepts to be able to mention the deception of one person to another in the performance of daily acts in which one of them can be harmed, where the harmful effects on both labor relations and the life of one of these subjects of rights [7]. Therefore, its investigative treatment is needed, for this, the present study defines the problem situation as the increase in infractions of labor rights by the employer in Ecuador. For its resolution, the main objective is to analyze the levels of deterioration of labor rights by employers in Ecuador.

2 Methods

2.1 Neutrosophic Statistics

Neutrosophic probabilities and statistics are a generalization of classical and imprecise probabilities and statistics. The Neutrosophic Probability of event E is the probability that event E will occur, the probability that event E will not occur, and the probability of indeterminacy (not knowing whether event E will occur or not). In classical probability $n_{sup} \leq 1$, while in neutrosophic probability $n_{sup} \leq 3^+$.

The function that models the neutrosophic probability of a random variable x is called the neutrosophic distribution: $NP(x) = (T(x), I(x), F(x))$. Where T(x) represents the probability that value x occurs, F(x) represents the probability that value x does not occur, and I(x) represents the undetermined or unknown probability of value x. Neutrosophic Statistics is the analysis of neutrosophic events and deals with neutrosophic numbers, the neutrosophic probability distribution [8], neutrosophic estimation, neutrosophic regression, etc.

It refers to a set of data, which is formed totally or partially by data with some degree of indeterminacy and the methods to analyze them. Neutrosophic statistical methods allow neutrosophic data (data that may be ambiguous, vague, imprecise, incomplete, or even unknown) to be interpreted and organized to reveal underlying patterns [9].

Finally, the Neutrosophic Logic [10], the Neutrosophic Sets, and the Neutrosophic Probabilities and Statistics have a wide application in various research fields and constitute a novel study reference in full development. Neutrosophic Descriptive Statistics comprises all the techniques for summarizing and describing the characteristics of neutrosophic numerical data [11, 21, 22, 23, 24].

Neutrosophic Numbers are numbers of the form $N = a + bI$, where a and b are real or complex numbers [12, 14, 15, 16,17], while "I" is the indeterminate part of the neutrosophic number N. The study of neutrosophic statistics refers to a neutrosophic random variable where X_l and X_u represents the lower and correspondingly higher level that the studied variable can reach, in an indeterminate interval $[I_l, I_u]$. Following the neutrosophic mean of the variable ($\bar{x}_N$) by the formula:

$$X_N = X_l + X_u I_N; I_N \in [I_l, I_u] \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Where, } \bar{x}_a = \frac{1}{n_N} \sum_{i=1}^{n_N} X_{il}, \bar{x}_b = \frac{1}{n_N} \sum_{i=1}^{n_N} X_{iu}, n_N \in [n_l, n_u], \tag{2}$$

is a neutrosophic random sample. However, for the calculation of neutral squares (NNS), it can be calculated as follows

$$\sum_{i=1}^n N(X_i - \bar{X}_{iN})^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n N \left[\begin{matrix} \min \left((a_i + b_i I_L)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_L), (a_i + b_i I_L)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_U) \right) \\ (a_i + b_i I_U)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_L), (a_i + b_i I_U)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_U) \\ \max \left((a_i + b_i I_L)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_L), (a_i + b_i I_L)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_U) \right) \\ (a_i + b_i I_U)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_L), (a_i + b_i I_U)(\bar{a} + \bar{b} I_U) \end{matrix} \right], I \in [I_L, I_U] \tag{3}$$

Where $a_i = X_l, b_i = X_u$. The variance of the neutrosophic sample can be calculated by

$$S_N^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_N} (X_i - \bar{X}_{iN})^2}{n_N}; S_N^2 \in [S_L^2, S_U^2] \tag{4}$$

The neutrosophic coefficient (CVN) measures the consistency of the variable. The lower the value of the CVN, the more consistent the performance of the factor is if compared to the other factors. The CVN can be calculated as follows [13, 18, 19, 20].

$$CV_N = \frac{\sqrt{S_N^2}}{\bar{x}_N} \times 100; CV_N \in [CV_L, CV_U] \tag{5}$$

The Neutrosophic Argumentation coefficient evaluates the criteria through Linguistic Terms with SVNN of consensus of justification of the expert opinion, (see Table 1).

Linguistic term	SVNN
No Deterioration (ND)	(1,0.05,0)
Almost No Deterioration (AND)	(0.95,0.12,0.15)
Very Low Deterioration (VLD)	(0.85,0.15,0.25)
Low Deterioration (LD)	(0.75,0.3,0.4)
Slight Deterioration (SD)	(0.65,0.35,0.5)
Deteriorated (D)	(0.55,0.45,0.53)
Mildly Deteriorated (MD)	(0.49,0.5,0.55)
Severely Deteriorated (SD)	(0.3,0.75,0.8)
Very Deteriorated (VD)	(0.25,0.8,0.85)
High Deterioration (HD)	(0.15,0.9,0.95)
Extremely Deteriorated (ED)	(0,0.95,1)

Table 1. Linguistic terms that represent the weight of the factors

3 Results

3.1 data collection

Statistics allows for analyzing situations in which random components contribute significantly to the variability of the data obtained. To measure the levels of risks associated with the treacherous, indeterminate random components are presented. The impossibility of measuring some determinants in labor rights is defined in the variability of responses of the surveys, similar to each other, that participated in the study.

3.2 Development of the Method

For the neutrosophic statistical modeling, the experts select five factors that prevail in the neutrosophic sets (elements associated with the violation of labor rights), based on defining the variable to be studied (Table 2).

Variable	Coding	Sample Factor	Scale
Levels of violation of labor rights by the employer in Ecuador	IDLE	[45;203]	[0; 1], $\forall F_n$ RCD = 0 (false) RCD = 1 (True) DCR $\neq$ 0.5 (Existing indeterminacy in IDLE)

Table 2. Characteristics of the variable. Source: own elaboration

It should be considered that the recommendations are subject to constant updates motivated by advances in the investigation of perfidy and the contributions of statistical information in university studies.

Factor	Root causes	Degree	Relationship between factor and set	Scale	Element Decision Acceptance Range
F1	Lack of prevention of occupational diseases and accidents	P	Neutrosophic set: (Occupational Health; accidents)	[0; 1]	Subset: • Index at risk of getting sick (high, medium, low, or null) • Level to be injured (high, medium, low, or none)
F2	Insecurity of the worker for the performance of his work activity	I	Neutrosophic set: (Job security, job performance)	[0; 1]	Subset: • Job security index (high, medium, low, or null) • Job performance (low, medium, high)
F3	Non-compliance with labor obligations by employers	O	Neutrosophic set: (Contractual obligations; violation of labor rights)	[0; 1]	Subset: • Contract compliance (low, medium, high) • Presence of the infraction (yes, sometimes, no)
F4	Lack of guarantees for the fulfillment of fundamental rights	G	Neutrosophic set: (Labor and contractual guarantee)	[0; 1]	Subset: • Labor guarantee: contractual guarantee (complies with some parameters or does not comply)
F5	Ignorance of the fundamental rights of the worker	C	Neutrosophic set: (knowledge; disclosure)	[0; 1]	Subset: • Unawareness; disclosure (high, medium, low, or none)

Table 3. Factors that give rise to the violation of labor rights. Source: own elaboration

For the development of the neutrosophic statistical study, it is recommended by the experts to analyze the levels of deterioration of the elements associated with labor rights in Ecuador. Studies in risk conditions are associated, based on the statistical bases and the surveys carried out (Table 4).

No.	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(1,0.05,0)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]
2	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0,0.95,1)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]
3	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]
4	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]
5	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0,0.95,1)]
6	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
7	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0,0.95,1)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]
8	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]
9	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
10	[(0,0.95,1);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]
11	[(0,0.95,1);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0,0.95,1)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]
12	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]
13	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]
14	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]
5	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]
16	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
17	[(0,0.95,1);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0,0.95,1)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]
18	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]
19	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(1,0.05,0)]
20	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]
21	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
22	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
23	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]

24	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]
25	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(1,0.05,0)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]
26	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(1,0.05,0)]
27	[(0,0.95,1);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0,0.95,1)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
28	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
29	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]
30	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]
31	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
32	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]
33	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(1,0.05,0)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]
34	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]
35	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
36	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]
37	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]
38	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
39	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
40	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]
41	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]
42	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]
43	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0,0.95,1)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(1,0.05,0)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
44	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]
45	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]
46	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(1,0.05,0)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0,0.95,1)]
47	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
48	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]

49	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]
50	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
51	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]
52	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]
53	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
54	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]
55	[(0,0.95,1);(0,0.95,1)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
56	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]
57	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]
58	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
59	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
60	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
61	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(1,0.05,0)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]
62	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]
63	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]
64	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
65	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]
66	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
67	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]
68	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(1,0.05,0)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]
69	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]
70	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]
71	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]
72	[(0,0.95,1);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0,0.95,1)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]
73	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]

74	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0,0.95,1)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
75	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]
76	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.95,0.12,0.15)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]
77	[(0,0.95,1);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.15,0.9,0.95)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
78	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]
79	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(1,0.05,0)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.65,0.35,0.5)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]
80	[(0.49,0.5,0.55);(0.75,0.3,0.4)]	[(0.15,0.9,0.95);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0,0.95,1);(0.25,0.8,0.85)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]
1-80	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.55,0.45,0.53)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]	[(0.25,0.8,0.85);(0.3,0.75,0.8)]	[(0.3,0.75,0.8);(0.49,0.5,0.55)]

Table 4. IDLE neutrosophic frequency. Source: own elaboration

For the development of the statistical study, the neutrosophic frequencies of the factors are analyzed to determine the *level of infraction of labor rights by the employer in Ecuador*, associated with risk conditions and labor guarantees. For each factor, a sample of the elements associated with the subset visualized by the group of experts is analyzed. The analysis of the sample that makes up the groups analyzed in the study with respect to determining the relationship between the deterioration of labor rights and the associated risk condition (Table 4).

For the modeling, it is decided to take each term to a neutrosophic number according to equation (1). Table 4 analyzes the IDLE level for a sample of [37; 80] workers and lawyers engaged in labor activity in Ecuador for each factor analyzed. Of the neutrosophic frequencies, it can be observed with a level of response in the weight of the factors, from the neutrosophic linguistic terms represented between [0; 1]. For each risk condition reviewed with a total indeterminacy level of $P = 19.8, I = 19.8, O = 20.9, G = 17.5, C = 20.1$, and with a representativeness level of [46.05%; 51.48%], on the days that both workers and lawyers are evaluated, in relation to more than one risk condition.

The preliminary results of the tracking have an indeterminate level close to 0.5 in F_1 . The result diagnoses the deterioration of each factor that affects the appearance of violations of the labor law of the employees according to the sample analyzed:

- The disease prevention index is severely deteriorated, while the level of workplace accidents is impaired for the interaction of the subsets analyzed.
- The worker's safety is in a severely deteriorated state in the face of a moderately deteriorated level of performance in their work activity.
- The level of contractual obligation is very deteriorated with moderately deteriorated in the violations of labor rights.
- The impact on labor and contractual guarantee It is very deteriorated with a slight influence on some institutions to a severely deterioration state.
- The lack of knowledge of the fundamental rights of the worker is severely deteriorated in the new environment that surrounds them, while there is a moderate deterioration in the disclosure of the rights of the workers.

Given the existing levels of indeterminacy, the use of classical statistics is not possible, so it is necessary to use neutrosophic statistics for a better understanding of interrelated neutrosophic sets.

3.3 Neutrosophic Statistical Analysis

The modeling of data on the level of deterioration existing in the factors associated with the origin of violations of labor rights and guarantees shows that factor 1 requires studies with a level of depth. To determine the level of incidence between the causes and conditions of occupational risk, it is necessary to analyze the means (Table 5). To understand what factor implies a representative mean, $\bar{x} = \in [\bar{x}_L; \bar{x}_U]$, the values of the neutrosophic means are calculated for the study of the variations of the affectations, and the values of the standard neutrosophic deviation $S_N \in [S_L; S_U]$. To determine which factor requires a higher level of accuracy at the time of diagnosing each subset, therefore, the $CV_N \in [CV_L; CV_U]$ values are calculated.

Factors	$\bar{x}_N$	S_N	CV_N
Lack of prevention of occupational diseases and accidents	0.29 + 0.538 I	0.015 + 0.331 I	0.052 + 0.615 I
Insecurity of the worker for the performance of his work activity	0.255 + 0.503 I	0.018 + 0.36 I	0.071 + 0.716 I
Non-compliance with labor obligations by employers	0.246 + 0.508 I	0.015 + 0.327 I	0.061 + 0.644 I
Lack of guarantees for the fulfillment of fundamental rights	0.239 + 0.458 I	0.015 + 0.298 I	0.063 + 0.651 I
Ignorance of the fundamental rights of the worker	0.264 + 0.515 I	0.015 + 0.342 I	0.057 + 0.664 I

Table 5. Neutrosophic statistical analysis of the IDLE level. Source: own elaboration

Table 5 shows the factors that affect the conditions of infringement of labor rights by the employer and the associated level of indeterminacy. So, it is necessary to analyze the status of workers and propose solutions to reduce violations of labor rights and guarantees. This means that the level of risk associated with this situation is more common and easier to detect, but there are levels of uncertainty to analyze. On the other hand, the analysis of CV_{No} for these factors is lower for the factors of *lack of prevention of occupational diseases and accidents and non-compliance with labor obligations by employers*.

Figure 1. Neutrosophic bar graph of the DPEA. Source: own elaboration

The neutrosophic set for the lack of prevention of occupational diseases and accidents and the breach of work obligations by employers derives with a greater frequency from the analyzed studies. It is visualized that, for levels of ignorance of the fundamental rights of the worker, where the knowledge and disclosure are defined in a contradictory way and the conditions of risk in labor rights (Figure 1).

3.4 Comparative Analysis

To determine the associated referent indeterminacy measure for $\bar{x} \in [\bar{x}_L; \bar{x}_U]$, $S_N \in [S_L; S_U]$ and $CV_N \in [CV_L; CV_U]$ to the form of neutrosophic numbers (Table 6). In the results obtained, it is observed that the values CV_N range from 0.052 to 0.071 with the measure of indeterminacy of [0.615; 0.716] generated by a sample of [100; 203] questionnaires and statistical information, obtained from 80 workers and lawyers.

From the results expected by the neutrosophic statistical study, it can be seen that:

The lack of prevention of occupational diseases and accidents causes a risk index of over 21.3% of those surveyed. The status of the analyzed factor is between severely deteriorated and deteriorated for a frequency of [23.2; 43].

The insecurity of the worker for the performance of his work activity presents an index of safety and job performance of 19.9% of those surveyed. While the factor status is between severely impaired and moderately impaired for a frequency of [20.4; 40.2].

The non-compliance with labor obligations by employers presents a level of labor infractions and contractual breaches of 20.1%. Therefore, the factor is between highly impaired and moderately impaired for a frequency of [19.7; 40.6].

The lack of guarantees for the fulfillment of fundamental rights presents a level of achievement of 18.2% of those surveyed. Therefore, the factor is very impaired to severely impaired with a frequency of [19.1; 36.6].

Ignorance of the fundamental rights of the worker presents a level of ignorance and disclosure of 20.4% of those surveyed. Therefore, the factor is between severely impaired and moderately impaired with a frequency of [21.1; 41.2].

For violations of labor rights by the employer, they increase with the deterioration of the factors analyzed. For these factors, more in-depth studies are required to track down the potential causes, such as the mitigation of the consequences that affect the fulfillment of labor rights. It is vital, for the analysis of statistical studies referring to the subject where the contradictions and indeterminacies are diversified in various degrees of weight in neutrosophic terms, to obtain a level of consensus of the specialists within the analyzed element of the neutrosophic set.

Factors	$\bar{x}_N$	S_N	CV_N
F1	0.29 + 0.538 I; I ∈ [0,0.461]	0.015 + 0.331; I ∈ [0,0.955]	0.052 + 0.615 I; I ∈ [0,0.915]
F2	0.255 + 0.503; I ∈ [0,0.493]	0.018 + 0.36; I ∈ [0,0.950]	0.071 + 0.716 I; I ∈ [0,0.901]
F3	0.246 + 0.508 I; I ∈ [0,0.516]	0.015 + 0.327 I; I ∈ [0,0.954]	0.061 + 0.644 I; I ∈ [0,0.905]

F4	$0.239 + 0.458$ $I;I \in [0,0.478]$	$0.015 + 0.298$ $I;I \in [0,0.950]$	$0.063 + 0.651$ $I;I \in [0,0.903]$
F5	$0.264 + 0.515$ $I;I \in [0,0.487]$	$0.015 + 0.342$ $I;I \in [0,0.956]$	$0.057 + 0.664$ $I;I \in [0,0.914]$

Table 6: Neutrosophic forms with the measure of indeterminacy. Source: own elaboration

6 Discussion

Partial Solutions

From the results obtained in the study, it is proposed to promote alternatives to minimize violations of labor rights committed by the employer. The variants presented allow the actions to be taken depending on the level of indeterminacy and acceptance of the levels in each range and for the tracking and prevention of *violations of labor rights by the employer*. Therefore, you want:

- Regularize and process a control system for perfidy, where the judicial system establishes entities and authorities responsible for regulating or punishing problems arising from poor labor relations between the parties involved in an employment contract. The labor inspector, the judge, and the labor inspectorate itself must carry out a procedure to sanction said actions.
- Inspectors are required to receive complaints arising from labor relations problems. Settlements are practiced when an employment relationship is terminated or when eviction or notice of termination of the contract is presented, either individually or collectively.
- The labor inspectorate as a judicial entity dependent on the public sector is in charge of receiving complaints related to labor problems that have no solution in labor relations. In addition, it acts as a body dependent on the Ministry of Labor, in charge of handling cases related to labor matters in Ecuador.
- Labor inspectors have a fundamental duty or objective to ensure effective compliance with the obligations imposed by law on workers and employers who are under a dependency employment relationship by signing an employment contract. To comply with the obligation to ensure compliance with hygiene and safety provisions in the workplace.
- Add the correct fulfillment of those obligations that the law imposes on both the employer and the worker. In addition, deny or grant requests for approval are imposed by the worker or the employer. Also impose the ends established in the norms of the Labor Code, carry out inspections in workplaces to be able to verify compliance with the dislocations of the Labor Code and in addition to the constitutional, legal, or regulatory norms in labor matters.

Conclusion

Labor Perfidy is applied in the action of hiring a worker, the same that is made visible in deception and acting in bad faith on the part of the employer. The need to get a job to support their homes and the lack of information and training makes workers, when starting an employment relationship, fall into this violation of rights since most workers do not know which authorities to contact in these cases.

The modeling showed the ignorance of the fundamental rights of the workers. As analyzed, the issue is not as well known in the social environment since most of the surveyed population has not heard about this problem and the danger that workers run when signing blank documents.

The violation of workers' rights is a very common problem in the labor sector. It is necessary to reform that adjusts to the principles and constitutional and legal rights of the worker, as is the case of Labor Perfidy. Therefore, the labor inspector is considered essential for the judicial and public systems to be able to carry out inspections of labor activities and to address power to ensure compliance with labor standards.

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